

Preliminary Design of a Standardized Off-Gas System for Fast Spectrum MSRs

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803884

ABSTRACT

Molten salt reactors are one of the six generation IV advanced reactor designs. The benefits of these reactors include higher operating temperature, online refueling, increased burn up, and compatibility with advanced fuel cycles. With these benefits come some downsides, one of which is the radioactive off gas continuously evolving from the fuel salt during operation. In this work a preliminary design is presented for a modular off-gas cleaning unit applicable to both fluoride and chloride fast spectrum MSRs. MSRs can be either fast or thermal designs, although the focus of this work will be on the fast variants. This design was conducted using an off-gas source term obtained through depletion-driven thermochemistry analysis of both fluorine and chlorine fast spectrum reactors. Simplified system models were used to model each component and predict component size, energy consumption, and maintenance schedule, respectively. The result of this work is preliminary design of a compact and portable off-gassing unit capable of managing the off-gas from fast spectrum MSR without human intervention.

Keywords: off gas, fission products, corrosion products, molten salt, fast reactors

1. INTRODUCTION

The Department of Energy (DOE) advanced reactor technology program (ART) exists with the goal of developing and deploying advanced reactors such as small modular reactors, microreactors, and full-scale GenIV designs. One of these GenIV designs; the molten salt reactor (MSR) is of particular interest due to its passive safety mechanisms, low operating pressure, and high operating temperature. Under the umbrella of MSRs there are both heterogeneous and homogeneous designs. In the liquid fuel design the heavy metal fuel is dissolved into a carrier salt and flowed through the reactor core; these designs also allow for online refueling. Unlike traditional light water reactors (LWR), liquid fueled MSRs will have gaseous products continuously evolving from the fuel [1]. This gas mixture will consist of fission products, acidic halogens, tritium, and various particulates. Although the majority of lanthanides and noble metals will remain in solution, a small fraction may become part of the off gas. Removing these gaseous products from the core will improve the reactors neutron economy and prevent the release of some of the high-activity fission products in the event of an accident.

Many past reports outline the processes and components that comprise a complete MSR off-gassing unit. In McFarlane et al. (2020) each step of the off-gassing process is discussed in detail, followed by proposed separation methods and technologies for each type of species being immobilized. Torres, R.D. et al. (2025) takes a more detailed approach, focusing on the specifics for each of the proposed technologies including decontamination factors as well as considerations of off-normal conditions [2]. Much work has also been done regarding components level analysis such as iodine immobilization [3,4,5] as well as noble gas containment and separation [6,7]. Management of tritium has been a topic of special interest to many researchers given its tendency to diffuse through structural material at high temperatures and form acidic halogen species [1]. Mays, G.T. et al. (1977) goes to great lengths to describe the behavior and distribution of tritiated species during the molten salt reactor experiment (MSRE) and the proposed MSBR [8]. Aside from MSBR, very little work exists regarding the required specifications of an off-gassing system for a nominally sized MSRs of both the fluoride and chloride variants. This work presents a preliminary design for a standardized off-gassing system applicable to full scale fast spectrum MSRs of both fluoride and

chloride composition. The final design will be an off-gassing system that can be easily installed into any MSR without modification to the reactor itself and operate without human intervention for an extended period. The final design should also be compact and portable, allowing the entire unit to be easily replaced when the service limit is reached.

2. Design Parameters

Before understanding the off-gassing system in its entirety, the composition of the off-gas must be well understood. The components in the gas stream can be categorized into several types of contaminants, each requiring its own removal method. To help coax the gaseous product out of the reactor core an inert sparge gas such as helium can be used. This means that not only do the components of the gas stream need to be immobilized but the off gas system to return a clean helium sparge gas back to the reactor core. Table 1 describes each class of off-gas species as well as some of the possible separation methods.

Table 1. Summary of off gas stream components and removal options

Off-gas Component	Example species	Removal Options
Mist, Aerosols, & Particulates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Noble metals - Graphite debris - Salt residual 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Particle traps - Chemical Scrubber - Dust cyclone
Tritiated Species	^3H , $^3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ^3HF , ^3HCl	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oxidize into water - Chemical scrubber
Halogens	F_2 , Cl_2 , I_2 , ICl , etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ag Zeolite sorbent - Chemical Scrubber
Reactive Gases	O_2 & N_2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Molecular sieve - Titanium getter
Inert Gases	Xe, Kr, Ar, He	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cryogenic distillation - Molecular Sieve

In addition to the species named in Table 1 short-lived radioisotopes will be present in the stream, all designs in literature stress the importance of implementing a decay tank into the system to allow for short-lived isotopes to be removed; this minimizes the decay heat entering the off-gas system [1]. The particulates can be removed through mechanical filtration; however, this may lead to issues with filter plugging; this is not ideal since our objective is to design a system with low maintenance demand. Acidic species, particulates, and halogens can all be removed with a scrubber, more specifically a molten hydroxide scrubber. ORNL has experimented with a eutectic hydroxide scrubber for the specific purpose of MSR off gas cleaning [9,10]. At saturation, the hydroxide scrubber will ideally allow only non-condensable gases and water to pass through, all of which can be removed with a series of molecular sieves. A molecular sieve will selectively filter each of the remaining components from the helium carrier gas.

3. Methodology

3.1. Computational Model

To track the evolution of the salts composition with respect to time, the reactors neutronics must be coupled to the thermochemical behavior of the system. This coupling was used by Tano, M.E. et al (2025) and coined "depletion-driven thermochemistry" [11]. Depletion was modeled by the open-source Monte Carlo code, OpenMC [12]. OpenMC will run several depletion steps, updating the isotopic concentration. At each step the isotopic concentrations are converted to elemental concentrations and given as input for the Gibbs energy minimization (GEM) code. Thermochemical behavior or characteristic will minimize the Gibbs free energy of the system and produce an updated species vector for both the dissolved fuel salt species and the gaseous species in the reactor's head space. The phase data from each step will be collected and the quantity of gas produced at each timestep will be averaged to determine the expected flow rate. The Molten Salt Thermochemical Database (MSTDB-TC) library can only track a limited number of species. Since Thermochemica cannot track hydrogen in its Gibbs energy model the amount of tritium produced will be acquired from the OpenMC depletion output and manually added to the gas vector. Once the gas vector is obtained, it will be passed to a series of simplified system models for each component in the system.

Figure 1. Workflow for the computation model

3.2. System Models for Off-Gas Filting Operations

The simple analysis methods used to model each of the system components are meant to obtain approximate sizing parameters which can serve as a starting point for higher fidelity analysis. The first stage of processing in the design is the array of dust cyclones which will be quantified using the Leith & Licht model which estimates the cyclone efficiency and pressure drop based upon its dimensions and the flow rate of the inlet gas [1]. The Langmuir isotherm model can predict gas adsorption on a solid adsorbent based upon a function representing the amount of adsorbed as a function of the gasses partial pressure [14,15]. Ideal adsorption solution theory (IAST) will capture competitive adsorption effects and produce adjusted isotherms. These adjusted isotherms were used in a modified Wheeler-Jonas breakthrough model to predict the service interval of the adsorbent beds [16]. The hydroxide scrubber operates on the principle of neutralizing acidic species with molecules of hydroxide. Conservative estimates for the breakthrough time of the hydroxide scrubber can be determined by deriving a hydroxide consumption rate based upon the hydroxide demand for each species in the gas as well as the molar flow rate of each species.

Most power consumption in the system comes from compressors and heaters. Compressor power was found using isentropic pressure and temperature relations. The efficiency of all compressors is assumed to be 70%, and the efficiency of all heaters is assumed to be 90%.

4. Design Overview

The results of both simulations and design decisions will be presented in this section. It was decided that the entire off-gas management unit should have a small physical footprint and operate for 5 years without requiring maintenance or human intervention. To keep the initial design simple, all radionuclides will be retained within the unit for its entire 5-year lifespan. After the unit has completed its 5-year duty it can be quickly swapped out. All MSRs require an emergency drain tank for their fuel salt to reside in case of an accident. This system must have passive cooling systems to remove the decay heat and can therefore also be used for off-gas decay heat. Most MSR designs intend to make use of the drain tank as their short term off-gas decay tank [1,17]. In this design it will be assumed that the off-gas stream entering the system has already passed through the reactors 2-hour decay system and will therefore be excluded from the design.

4.1. Off Gas Source Term

After averaging the Thermochemica gas production terms for each time step it was determined that around 490 moles of gas will be produced every 100 days in the fluoride system and around 390 moles in the chlorine system. Of this stream much of the gas will consist of xenon, krypton, and helium. In the chloride system argon will be present in greater concentration because of chlorine neutron capture reactions. In both streams several particulate and halogen species will be present in trace amounts. It will be assumed that all the hydrogen introduced into the system will form HF in the fluoride system and HCl in the chloride system. Although this is not necessarily true it is an approximation that errors on the side of

caution. During MSRE, components of the oil used to lubricate the fuel pumps were finding their way into the gas stream [1]. Combining the effects of fuel splashing and pyrolysis oil with a more complete thermochemical model will yield a larger, more realistic off-gas source term. The consideration of such effects is beyond the scope of this work.

4.2. Cyclone Separation

The goal of the cyclone stage is to remove most particulates present in the gas and in turn lighten the load of the hydroxide scrubber. To remove these particulates, the flow will need to undergo a pressure drop, in fact, the largest pressure drop in the system will in this first step. The inlet gas will be at a temperature of 400K and at 6 bar, respectively. The temperature was chosen to be 400K because this is the temperature limit of the Leith & Licht model. One characteristic of the gas that must be known is the diameter of the particle being targeted for removal. Cyclones become less efficient as the particle size decreases meaning that the smaller particulates will be less significant. Typically, particles far below the μm scale are not easily removed. Halides and entrained fuel salt components will form smaller particles whereas the metallic species are more likely to form larger particulates ($>1\mu\text{m}$) [18]. For this reason, gases, halogens, and entrained fuel salt components are expected to pass through the cyclone with minimal removal. The efficiency of the cyclone will be determined by several parameters such as the quality of the vortex produced by the gas; this vortex behavior requires high gas velocity. In this case, we are working with a low flow rate, low pressure system which means that the cyclone itself will need to be small and multiple stages will be required. The result of this analysis was a 5x5 cyclone array with each cyclone having a diameter of 10.2 cm.

Table 2. Performance properties of the cyclone array

Single Stage Efficiency	9.32 %
Pressure Drop (single stage)	7.59 kPa
Overall Efficiency	91.34 %

4.3. Molten Hydroxide Scrubber

The molten hydroxide scrubber is undoubtedly the most complex component of the system and is difficult to properly analyze with non-computational methods. The design chosen for this work is based upon the ORNL scrubber design discussed in [9,10]. The molten hydroxide will be a eutectic NaOH-KOH (51-49) mixture. This eutectic will enter from the top of the vessel through a sprayer and gets deposited on a packed bed. The gas will flow in the opposite direction through the packed bed contacting the molten hydroxide and neutralizing the acidic species. Noble gases as well as oxygen and nitrogen will pass through without interacting [1]. The service limit of the scrubber will need to be determined by the amount of hydroxide consumed. This means that only the chemical component of breakthrough is being considered. To ensure that the system is mass transfer limited then velocity of the gas through the scrubber was limited to be on the order of 1 cm/s. The length of the reaction vessel was then set to be 60 cm, allowing the gas to have a full minute of residence time. Below are the dimensions used for the hydroxide scrubber design.

Table 3. Specifications of the molten hydroxide scrubber

Scrubber Length	64 cm
Scrubber Radius	20 cm
Hydroxide Temperature	470 k
Total Hydroxide Loading	8.62 kg
Pressure Drop	0.4 bar

4.4. Water Trap

The duty of the water trap is determined directly by the amount of HF and iodine neutralized in the scrubber. It is assumed that all HF and iodine are converted to water and escapes the hydroxide scrubber. Water has a molecular diameter of 2.65 Å and will be easily captured by a 3Å molecular sieve. The 3Å

molecular sieve will only adsorb water vapor and helium, all other species in the stream are too large and will pass through. The adsorption of helium onto the 3A sieve will be weak with a maximum helium absorption of 0.01 mol/kg at over 19 MPa [14]. Based upon the breakthrough time, the water trap will need to contain over 16 kg of 3A sieve if it is to operate continuously for 5 years before replacement. The size of the water trap is directly related to the amount of hydrogen produced during reactor operation. It should be noted that although the water removal demands are small this won't be the case for a thermal reactor where the hydrogen production will be more significant.

Table 4. Specifications of the water trap

Radius	12 cm
Length	50 cm
Adsorbent Mass	16.512 kg
Pressure Drop	7.64 kPa

4.5. Halide Trap

Adsorption isotherm data is not available for iodine or inter halogen species therefore the service interval must be determined based upon maximum adsorption capacity. In the case of the halide trap the chosen adsorbent is Ionex AG-900 which can capture roughly 25% of its weight in iodine [20]. Due to kinetic effects the iodine may breakthrough before the maximum adsorption capacity is reached. To account for this the calculated amount of required adsorbent is multiplied by 4 to ensure that breakthrough does not occur within 5 years. The parameters of the halide trap are shown below.

Table 5. Specifications of the halide trap

Radius	5 cm
Length	25 cm
Adsorbent Mass	1.845 kg
Pressure Drop	Negligible

4.6. Joule Thompson Loop

After flowing through the water trap the gas can be cooled to near room temperatures to improve the performance of the remaining adsorbent beds. The flow rate of off-gas is low and only requires a small amount of heat transfer (around 500 W) which can be achieved with a Joule -Thompson loop. In the Joule Thompson loop the refrigerant is first compressed to a heated, high-pressure state. The heated fluid is then passed to an air-cooled coil to reject the heat generated from compression. After the coil, the refrigerant is expanded through a joule-Thompson valve where it will rapidly decrease in temperature according to the specific Joule-Thompson coefficient (μ).

4.7. Helium Separation

The final step of the gas cleaning process is to separate helium from the rest of the stream so that it can be supplied back to the reactor core or reuse. For this task a 13x zeolite adsorbent will be used which should capture all particles with a molecular diameter less than 10 Å. This includes Oxygen, Xenon, Nitrogen, Krypton, and Argon. If done properly, Zeolite adsorbents can be regenerated several times before a decrease in performance is seen [20]; in this case the number of regeneration cycles will be limited to 10. To allow the adsorbent beds to be regenerated without disrupting the flow of gas from the reactor, several beds will be used in parallel. In both the fluoride and chloride cases the first species to breakthrough was xenon due to its high concentration. The amount of time a bed is allowed to operate before regeneration is therefore determined by the breakthrough time of xenon. To allow for 5 years of continuous operation, it was found that 5 beds of 13x zeolite could be used each measuring 38 cm in diameter, 200 cm in height, and containing

over 160 kg of adsorbent. Based upon the xenon breakthrough time and the allowance of 10 cycles, regeneration would be required every 42 days.

Table 6. Specifications of 13x adsorbent beds

Radius	19 cm
Length	200 cm
Adsorbent Mass	161.581 kg
Pressure Drop	0.2406
Time Before Regeneration	42 days

The purpose of the regeneration process is to restore the adsorbent back to its original state by removing the adsorbed particles from the adsorption sites. This can be done at low temperatures under vacuum, or at elevated temperatures with a counter flowing purge gas; it is important that the temperature of the adsorbent does not exceed 450 C [20]. This design will use the heated purge gas method. The purge gas of choice is helium and will flow through the adsorbent bed in the opposite direction as the initial off-gas stream. The helium will start off at atmospheric temperature and 1.5 bar, but slowly be ramped up to 573 K. The temperature ramp rate should be in the range of 5-10 C/min to avoid thermally stressing the zeolite. Once the regeneration temperature is reached the purge gas will continue to flow for several hours, ensuring all contaminants have been removed [20].

4.8. Power Consumption

For the sake of being conservative, the inlet gas is assumed to be at near atmospheric pressure, and it must be compressed to 6 bar before entering the cyclone array. To achieve the total 6:1 compression ratio three stages will be used, each having a compression ratio of 2. The total power consumption across all three 3 stages was found to be 1.445 kW, assuming 70% compressor efficiency. To store the contaminated purge gas in the long-lived decay tanks, the gas needs to be brought from 1.5 bar to 400 bar and will require 9 stages. The required input power for the compressor was found to be 7.276 kW; the other component of the regeneration system is the inline gas heater which is estimated to consume 966.129 W. The mass flow rate through the Joule-Thompson compressor is substantially higher than the other two compressors considered and will therefore have a for greater power demand. Using two stages and a 70% compressor efficiency, the required power was estimated to be 14.572 kW.

Table 7. Power Consumption estimates for each subsystem

Pre-Cyclone Compressor	1.445 kW
Storage Compressor	7.276 kW
Gas Heater	966 W
Joule-Thompson Compressor	14.572 kW
Total Power Consumption w/o Regeneration	16.017 kW
Total Power Consumption during Regeneration	22.748 kW

A: molten hydroxide scrubber, **B:** long-lived decay tanks, **C:** helium separation, **D:** cyclone array, **E:** Purge gas storage, **F:** water trap, **G:** halide trap, **H:** footprint of a 20' container, **I:** gas heater, **J:** Joule-Thompson heat exchanger

Figure 2. CAD rendering of the final design

5. CONCLUSIONS

The MSR is one of the most promising Generation IV designs because of their unique capabilities; fast MSRs can offer additional advantages. Despite all benefits that MSRs have to offer, much uncertainty regarding the near-term feasibility of their operation has hindered their development. This work addresses one of the most pressing issues: managing the radioactive off gas. The architecture put forth serves as a starting point for future work toward developing such an off-gas system. This design focuses on modularity and reliability to ensure that the system can be economical and safe. It was shown that such a system could be designed to operate without human intervention for an extended period. The Preliminary design of the off-gas system for fast spectrum MSRs is presented and discussed.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank both the DOE SULI and INL internship programs for the opportunity to complete this work. The author would also like to acknowledge Dr. Piyush Sabharwall and Dr. Mauricio Tano for their support.

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